

**Community-Managed Piped Water Supply:
*Issues and Challenges***

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Abstract

The performance of government supported piped water supply schemes can be improved with strong state-recognized community organizations in place that receive support to maintain service levels. Well-functioning committees and the larger involvement of beneficiaries in decision-making and implementation of piped water supply solutions can increase the efficiency of the operations, improve effectiveness/sustainability, enhance user satisfaction and lead to better equity outcomes. Financing mechanism under programmes such as Jal Jeevan Mission should enable full life-cycle costs to be met, particularly capital maintenance and post construction support.

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As a part of its commitment to Goal 6.1 to achieve universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water for all by 2030, Government of India (GoI) has been endeavouring to deliver water supply facilities. However, 163 million people do not have access to safe water as of 2017 (Sarkar, 2019). As per NITI Aayog in 2019, only 25% of households have access to safe drinking water i.e., receiving 55 litres per capita per day (lpcd) on-premises and “about 20% of rural households have piped water access” (MoJS, 2021).

Jal Jeevan Mission (JJM) rolled out in June 2019 by GoI aims to provide functional household tap connection to every rural household by 2024. The mission that expands on the National Rural Drinking Water Programme (NRDWP) guidelines, 2013 provides a renewed thrust towards household level access to piped water supply to all on-premises. It calls for the involvement of the Gram Panchayats (GPs) in planning and implementation of the project, proposes performance-based funding to states, and ensures mandatory participation of women in Village Water and Sanitation Committees (VWSCs). Estimates indicate that for closing the gap in access in rural India as a part of JJM, the “expected cost of operationalizing is around Rs. 3.6 trillion” (*The Economic Times*, 2019).

Insights on Community-Managed Piped Water Supply

JJM focuses on small scale, community managed, groundwater schemes wherever possible, with emphasis on source sustainability through groundwater recharge and wastewater reuse. “Community participation in piped water supply is sought not only under the recent JJM but is also an inbuilt component of various national and state flagship programmes” (Bora, 2019). All rural water supply schemes are to be operated and maintained by local bodies such as GPs, VWSCs, Zila Panchayats (ZPs) and civil

society organizations as per the 73rd Amendment to the Constitution of India, 1992.

The JJM as well as some of the programmes by the state governments are committed to delivering higher levels of service on-premises via piped networks as regards access, quality and reliability. State support and handholding by the implementation support agency is of crucial importance for the piped water supply to be sustainable and successful.

A study suggests that “centrally managed drinking water supply programs used conventional engineering solutions that resulted in an infrastructure that was beyond the people’s capability to maintain” (Lane, 2004). Water infrastructure fell into disrepair, and users were unable or unwilling to maintain it themselves. The need for better operation and maintenance (O&M) capacities and better management capacity of the user institution constitutes a problem for large piped networks and multi-village schemes.

However, the challenges of providing access to groups belonging to various castes/sections in rural settings may pose social and political challenges, which go far beyond technical/financial issues. Studies point to the complexity of managing multiple stakeholders, the reasons for the success of these schemes and the challenges encountered in planning, operations and maintenance.

Institutional Arrangements and Capacity Building

Successful cases of community engagement typify community planned and managed schemes that are demand-responsive serving the needs of the user and where infrastructure investments were made through government, donor or NGO programmes. A drinking water user committee is formed, and given basic training and the scheme’s responsibility handed over to them. Post-

construction support is provided to the communities mainly through the local government and the communities are not left to manage the schemes on their own. Piped water supply continues in such schemes often for decades and service levels are being maintained, and the sections of the network that have begun to deteriorate are being replaced.

Community-based action and supportive institutional dynamics play a key role in successful cases and community leaders, community-based organizations along with panchayat representatives such as ward members/*sarpanches*, implementation support agency, state department and other frontline workers are sometimes actively involved in grassroots mobilisation, spreading awareness towards the adoption of the piped water supply scheme. Further, the community receives direct support on technical aspects, finance and materials from the local government/local implementation support agency or NGO. The NGO at places works on aligning and supporting the government processes and provides expertise and momentum to the initiative.

Cases marked by strong institutional arrangements with clearly defined strategies and effective demarcation of roles and functions perform well. The formal recognition normally helps the committee in opening and operation of bank accounts and is also a necessity to support receipt of funds from the GP. The control of the water systems rests on these institutions which are spearheading the initiative. They are responsible for O&M as well as service provisioning.

For community management of piped water supply to be sustained-at-scale, the newly formed institutions would need strong leadership, clarity on ownership and long-term techno-managerial, significant financial and materials support to community institutions by the external donor and/or implementation support agencies/state agencies (local

government) on key duties including operation, maintenance and administration. These community institutions are entrusted with the responsibility of articulating collective demand for drinking water systems as well as to collaborate and/or negotiate with the local/state government agencies for the fulfilment of their water needs and aspirations.

The capacities of the community institution responsible for O&M and service provision on the management aspects of the system need to be improved. Further, these community institutions which are normally voluntary need to be legally recognized as the service provider. It may not be possible for the elected water committee to manage all the day-to-day O&M and administration work related to the piped water supply, and this may necessitate the sub-contracting of some of their tasks to a trained individual(s).

Apart from general awareness-raising in villages regarding the scheme, the committee needs to undergo an intensive preparatory period of capacity building before/during and after the construction of piped water supply. Only then will a collective initiative emerge from the community to take the responsibility for effective O&M of the scheme.

Gender and Social Inclusion

More thought needs to go into equity and gender considerations while designing the institutional arrangements, tariffs and technical design of the systems. Formal arrangements are needed where poorest households from socially marginalized groups, female-headed households etc., are exempt from payment. Overall, the tariff should take into consideration the community's ability to pay.

There is a need to actively promote women's role beyond just recipients of water services, and ensure through good gender

mainstreaming, practices that play an important role in the O&M of piped water supply. A gender-balanced community oversight role can be ensured through building the capabilities of the women in the management of piped water supply. A quota exists in the VWSC rules already for women; the programme can ensure that at least 50% of the community facilitators and service providers (pump operator) must be women. In general, care should be taken to maintain a fifty-fifty balance in the percentage of men and women engaged in initiating, siting, implementing, using, and O&M of piped water supply for proper gender mainstreaming.

Financial Sustainability

To sustain and expand the piped water supply scheme coverage at the designed service level delivery, ensure sustainability and to deal with its inefficiencies, there is a need to have a financing strategy based on a sound understanding of capital investment needs, operating expenditure, financial flows, different sources of funding and depreciation costs. Low sustainability of capital investments in most cases can be traced to the fact that while infrastructure is available, there is a lack of investment in asset maintenance i.e., there is a paucity of funds for operating costs. This undermines the continuous supply of services, and can eventually lead to facilities that underperform or go defunct.

Institutional support costs need to be considered right from the start as this helps maintain the expected service levels into account such as on capacity-building of local institutions or service providers (pump operator/mechanic), monitoring of water quality, administration (book-keeping etc.) as well as the enforcement of regulations. For the schemes to be scalable, attention needs to be paid to cost-effective innovations that lead to better operational standards. The JJM apart from incentivizing adequate governance is also injecting public funds into capital

investments. There needs to be more clarity on the maintenance and the covering of operating costs and if a regular allocation of additional public funds would be done for them through GP funds for community-managed piped water supply services. It is still not clear whether water tariffs will be charged that enable the recovery of operating costs, as well as the depreciation costs and a surplus created to reduce dependence on government subsidies. Overall, there is a need to develop capacities to handle/monitor expenditure as well as the service level in the piped water supply to improve the accountability systems in the sector.

Source Sustainability

The success of the piped water supply also depends on source sustainability as well as the technology choice and construction quality of the infrastructure. Source sustainability needs to be taken into consideration during the design stage to maintain the desired quantity and water quality standard throughout the design life of the piped water supply. The depletion of water levels in groundwater and surface water sources is considered to be a major constraint along with water contamination due to saltwater ingress, fluoride, arsenic or other geogenic contaminants.

To address this, there is a need to shift focus from dependence on a single source to multiple sources. Also, water budgeting needs to be done to ensure household-level drinking water security. Issues related to reject management need to be addressed so that the contaminants do not re-enter into water, environment or food. Groundwater aquifer recharge through recharge structures and surface water harvesting needs to be prioritized.

Way Forward

The functionality of community-managed piped water supply schemes in rural settlements can be sustained with strong state-recognized community organizations in place that receive “external technical, managerial, financial, and social resources to maintain service levels” (Hutchings et al, 2015; Machado et al, 2019). Experience from the ground indicates that well-functioning committees and the larger involvement of beneficiaries in decision-making and implementation of piped water supply solutions can increase the efficiency of the operations, improve effectiveness/sustainability, enhance user satisfaction and lead to better equity outcomes.

VWSCs are a mandated standing committee of the GP but rarely exist on the ground. These need to be created and their capacities strengthened. “When decentralized schemes are functioning at a habitation level; a local water management committee often has to be created. There needs to be a mechanism for recognition of sub-committees of the GP and VWSC to manage decentralized water supply schemes. This formal recognition will ease opening and operation of bank accounts and can support receipt of funds from the GP” (Bora, 2019).

While an enabling environment has been created through dedicated national/ state/district level organizations and specially designed units with the formal mandate to build institutions as well as develop professional capacities to manage them, for sustainable services delivery, a combination of community engagement and continued state support is required. This backed by the state’s long term responsibility for service provision and support – technical, financial (deficit financing as only a part of O&M costs can be raised through tariff) and managerial to handle the services can go a long way in improving the functioning and sustainability of the system. “The VWSCs should be

professionalized to take over the operation, administration and management of the systems. The operator should be trained or a cadre of self-employed mechanics developed in the area for minor repairs and the committee should be aware of the supply chain for spares/services needed by the system to reduce the downtime period for repair” (Bhaduri, 2020).

Financing mechanism under programmes such as JJM should enable full life-cycle costs to be met, particularly capital maintenance and post construction support. GPs should play an important part in leveraging resources to support capital maintenance expenses i.e., major repairs and replacement. There should be clear tariff policy in place to enable operational expenses recovery along with subsidy mechanism to support the marginalized. There is a need to prepare local government annual maintenance and medium-term asset management plan and ring-fence budgets. Also, pooled support and financing mechanisms need to be established for major capital maintenance by local governments.

The technical agency of the government should provide close supervision as well as undertake inspection and audit of installations, replacement of spare parts and preventive maintenance. Under JJM, the capacities of the state, district and block need to be strengthened and institutional support through Block Resource Centres/Institutional Support Agency/cadres of Community Resource Persons (CRPs) etc., is needed to scale up the capacity-building interventions in state-wide programmes on piped water supply. This needs to be provided for high levels of post-construction support to the community managed system.

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